

Deliverable 6.1

RETHINK Dissemination and outreach strategy

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Introduction

The overall objective of RETHINK is to provide recommendations and guidelines to maintain and improve the quality of interactions in the new science communication landscape. RETHINK aims to provide support to re-examine and re-orientate science communication across Europe. Over the course of the project, a wide variety of actors will be mobilized and several types of data will be collected and used.

Deliverable 6.1 RETHINK Dissemination and Outreach Strategy is the second deliverable of Work Package 6 “ENGAGE: communication and dissemination”, led by SISSA Medialab. It presents RETHINK target audiences, the messages and narratives that the project will create to capture its audience’s attention and further involvement in the different stages of the project.

This is followed by a detailed explanation of the objectives and steps of the Dissemination and Outreach Strategy, all different aspects converging to the following aims: reaching the target groups in an efficient, creative and meaningful way, supporting the project’s contents and paving the path for a sustainable legacy. Finally, a set of guidelines are provided, that aim to facilitate all partners’ work whilst creating engaging communication pieces.

RETHINK overview

Open and productive interactions between science and society are vital for a healthy democracy. The relationship between science and the rest of society is a crucial aspect of how our society develops and addresses societal challenges such as food security and climate change. Fruitful interactions between science and society are not straightforward, as recent controversies have shown.

We need an approach to science communication that is able to nurture interactions between science and society in an open and reflexive way. However, the science communication landscape itself is undergoing deep and fundamental changes due to two interrelated changes.

First, the boundaries between science and society have become blurred. Interactions and interfaces between science and other fields in society such as economics, politics, art and culture have become more numerous and diverse. Second, digitalization has revolutionized the science communication landscape. It has fundamentally changed how scientists; other R&I stakeholders and a variety of publics interact and communicate.

These developments require us to rethink the newly emerging science communication landscape to ensure the quality of interactions between the actors involved. In the context of emerging digital media, it has become relatively easy to disregard scientific evidence as 'just another opinion'. At the same time, at least part of the scientific community still struggles with the lingering yet false assumption that deficits in public knowledge (referred to as the 'deficit model') are the central factor in social conflicts and controversies about science, while in fact underlying interests, moral values and cultural beliefs have a much larger role in shaping public views about science.

It is a time of great opportunity to open science and create meaningful connections with society if the right conditions are created. The RETHINK project encompasses

today's key manifestations of science communication with a particular focus on the digital sphere where scientists, science communicators and various publics exchange information, ideas and concerns and where challenges, but also opportunities exist to open up science and form meaningful connections.

Aim and approach of RETHINK

How can the theory and practice of science communication contribute to a productive relationship between science and society, supporting the opening up of research and innovation practices whilst simultaneously maintaining and improving the quality of interactions amongst the actors involved? Professional science communicators have always been key catalysts of meaningful interactions at the interface between science and society, building bridges between experts, policymakers and society as a whole. How can they continue to play this vital role in the newly emerging landscape bringing together a seemingly endless variety of actors, activities, communicative spaces and sensemaking practices?

Against this backdrop, the RETHINK project aspires to rethink science communication, both its theory and practice, to accommodate the major challenges to the individual and collective process of making sense about science. We focus on everyday practices of making sense about science and recognize that sense-making is not only about basic scientific knowledge, but also about a range of other aspects, such as how science works, the limits of scientific knowledge, the important of economic, social, political and ethical dimensions and the legitimacy of a variety of values and perspectives that are present in the public conversation about science. Scientific understanding may provide part of the solution to a social problem, but not all of it. An open and reflexive approach to the complexities of sensemaking is crucial to address social conflicts and controversies arising in the interaction between science and society. Even if past years have seen a growing number of participation mechanisms and deliberative forums mushroom, these coexist with a big number of European citizens that rely on mediated communication to make sense about science in relation to social issues.

With these notions in mind, a guiding principle of RETHINK is that the contextual knowledge of citizens across the EU should play a vital role in shaping future scientific and technological developments and the sharing of this knowledge should be facilitated. We eventually aim to improve the quality of interactions between science and society by providing concrete recommendations and training resources for nurturing open and reflexive science-society interfaces. The following diagram explains how the project is structured and how it works towards its final goal “A European science communication ecosystem that is open, inclusive, reflexive and adaptive”.

Important EC definitions

The EC shares the following definitions, in the document “Making the most of your H2020 Project” published by the European IPR Helpdesk in 2018, with the aim that all project beneficiaries have a common understanding of these concepts:

Communication: “Communication on projects is a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.” It’s objective is to reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g. by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges. It focuses on informing about and promoting the project and its results/success.

Dissemination: “The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.” Its objective is to transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising the impact of EU-funded research. It focuses on describing and ensuring results are available for others to use.

Exploitation: “The utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities.” Its objective is to effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society. It focuses on making concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use).

The boundaries between the three concepts are often times blurry and may overlap. An article written for communication purposes can be at the same time a dissemination piece, when it is shared as a final document. The intersections of these three areas

enrich the grounds for enhancing the presence and the outreach of the project in different arenas. On the bottom line, these three actions aim to maximizing the impact of the project.

“**Results**” is a concept defined in H2020 guidelines as follows:

“Any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.”

(Source: EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary/Reference Terms)

In a nutshell, results encompass all project outcomes that may be used by the project partners or other relevant stakeholders outside the project. They have the potential to be either commercially exploited (e.g. concrete products or services) or lay the foundation for further research, work or innovations (e.g. novel knowledge, insights, technologies, methods, data).

Links to helpful documents and resources

1. [Communicating EU research and innovation: guidance for project participants](#)
2. [You Tube Channel: The EU Guide to Science Communication](#)
3. [60-minute workout to increase the communication impact of your project](#)
4. [Social Media Guide for EU funded R&I projects](#)

Audiences and messages

RETHINK activities and outcomes are mainly addressed to a vast range of science communication actors. Therefore, the main categories of target audiences that RETHINK will address are:

1. The scientific community

The community of researchers and academics is an important target group. Scientists play a key role in increasing the accuracy and trust in science communication. They will be reached through publications, attendance at conferences and leveraging of existing networks. We will ensure that all publications produced by the work of this project will be Open Access. Publications will be made available via a green and gold access route depending on the publisher.

Message: RETHINK messages to researchers and academics will focus on how to support and engage them in the improvement, accuracy and reliability of science communication in their work and resources. The Rethinkerspaces will play a key role in this process, engaging scientists in debates on science communication, and enhancing their understanding of citizens' sensemaking of science.

2. Science journalists and “traditional” science communicators

Science journalists and “traditional” science communicators play a key role in science-society interfaces. Some of RETHINK outcomes will be specifically addressed to this target group, such as the one brief focused on how they can improve their activities as science communicators and science journalists, especially in terms of how to increase the accuracy of (and therefore trust in) science communication.

Message: RETHINK messages to science journalists and “traditional” science communicators will focus on engaging them in making use of RETHINK outcomes and not only – engage in reflective practices and keep up to date on innovative ideas and strategies that emerge from science communication research. Special attention will be dedicated to disseminating project results to them, such as training modules, short

briefs, best practices, and a new role typology for opening up science and innovation to society.

3. “Unconventional” science communicators

Digitalization has made individuals turn from being a passive audience into active producers of media content. Nowadays, some of the main influencers in the field of science communication, do not identify any more with the standard categories of science journalists and traditional science communicators. They are for example scientists who promote research through their own blog or social media accounts, or hobbyists and independent source of science news, users who are particularly passionate about a topic and share a lot of information about it through their public channels.

Message: RETHINK messages to “unconventional” science communicators will share the same objective as the above – make use of RETHINK outcomes to ameliorate the way they help citizens make sense of the sea of information they have access to, and making it accessible to those for whom information about science is not currently freely available. This is particularly important considering that quite often, “unconventional” science communicators have no specific training for doing so. RETHINK message towards them will focus on the importance of accuracy and trust, and provide suggestions for new and effective strategies to maintain and improve the quality of their interactions with society.

4. Policy makers

Policy makers play a key role in supporting open and reflexive science-society interfaces. Specific guidelines will be produced, specifically addressed to policy makers. This will be one of the main project outcomes which will be disseminated to this target audience through conferences and events, along with an improved set of criteria and indicators adjusted to the specific needs and features of the new science communication landscape.

Message: RETHINK messages to policy makers will focus on engaging them in ways they can support the uptake of the project outcomes, and play an active role in

promoting more efficient science communication practices, including support for training activities to key stakeholders.

5. General public, including "Hard-to-reach audiences"

The public in general, and "hard-to-reach audiences" in particular, will be engaged in the project from its early stage, through data collection processes. This will help better understand their sensemaking practices, and therefore develop better tailored recommendations for scholars and practitioners at a later stage in the project. The involvement of social inclusion and gender experts in the project European sounding board will also help with this process.

Message: RETHINK messages to the general public and "hard-to-reach" audiences will focus on engaging them in project activities. In particular, we will underline the value that their participation will bring about in the understanding of sensemaking processes and how they are influenced by current new forms of science communication.

Communication and dissemination strategy

Communication objectives

RETHINK main focus is to bridge the gap between science communication theory and practice and develop training resources as well as recommendations for more open and reflexive science communication. RETHINK outcomes will contribute to raising awareness of the importance of reflective practices in science communication, as well as share innovative ideas and strategies within the broad science communication community.

Following the EC definition for communication, which can be summarized as “a planned set of activities that reach out to different publics, informing about impact and benefits”, RETHINK communication objectives are to:

1. Raise awareness about new, effective science communication forms and practices among all the target groups and the broad segment of the public;
2. Engage our target audiences with aspirational contents and activities, always in consideration of the need to embrace underserved audiences, considering gender-balanced information and representations;
3. Provide a unified approach to communications, including a common public image;
4. Establish sustainable tools and structures for the project including the different communication channels, printed materials, website and social media;
5. Disseminate the outcomes and results of the project to all relevant target groups, enhance the visibility of RETHINK project objectives, activities and outcomes, during all its phases;
6. Leverage the dissemination potential of all partners and third parties;
7. Support the communication of the partners at the local and national level.

As core principles of our communication strategy, RETHINK will:

- Share stories that matter: We will always try to find or build a point of connection with our audiences. For this, we will develop a deep understanding of the local

contexts where our actions are taking place. We will partner with each Rethinkerspace coordinator, in order to get feedback about the interests and shared experiences of the local participants.

- Talk about the real world, not abstract ideas: In each country, we will reach out to members of all the above-mentioned target groups. Rethinkerspaces' coordinators (in Italy, the Netherlands, UK, Sweden, Poland, Serbia and Portugal) will play a key role in engaging with local actors, and we will support them with communication materials when needed, as well as our social media channels. We will pay special attention to sharing an understanding of sensemaking practices and science communication research outcomes that is easy understandable by all stakeholders involved.
- Present the project and its outputs to the broader European science communication community, in order to improve the understanding of current sensemaking practices, and ameliorate science engagement, while creating a stronger link between research and practice in science communication. The JCOM-RETHINK community page will strongly contribute to this scope.

This strategy will be executed by the whole RETHINK consortium. SISSA Medialab will regularly gather feedback from each Work Package leader, in order to keep updated about their ongoing activities.

Dissemination objectives

Summarizing the EC definition of Dissemination as “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate ensuring results available for others to use” the following are the key OurSpace Dissemination objectives:

1. run an effective and tailored communication and dissemination plan to ensure the best impact of project results;
2. develop a comprehensive set of communications materials to ensure a successful positioning of the project, exposure and delivery of its results;
3. leverage and harness the dissemination channels;

4. create the foundations for a robust legacy.

Tools and channels

In order to successfully communicate our messages and content, RETHINK will use the following tools and channels to support communication and dissemination actions, with an important focus on two-way exchange with audiences.

Visual identity

The aim of the visual identity is to create an attractive and identifiable branding for the project that is appealing to the target groups and make the project distinct.

The visual identity of RETHINK comprises all the elements that are part of the visual identity guidelines: the RETHINK core logo, the 4 different color versions, the set of fonts to be used in all official documents and a set of icons that will enrich visually all our communication and dissemination products. It also includes templates necessary for all the project's purposes.

GUIDELINES VISUAL IDENTITY RETHINK

The visual identity guidelines were developed by the [InMedia Solutions](#) company based in Barcelona, which has been selected through a call for tenders. A complete version is downloadable in the [WP6 folder](#) of the shared online management portal Edugroepen.

Website

The project website is the main window to the world and the platform where project outcomes, news and activities will be shared. It has been created using Wordpress, by a webdesigner from the [InMedia Solutions](#) company. Contents have been provided by SISSA Medialab. The RETHINK website URL is www.rethinkscicomm.eu and the current homepage is the following:

Home About the project Who we are EU Sounding Board Updates Contact us

RETHINK

The RETHINK project aspires to rethink science communication, both its theory and practice, to accommodate the major challenges to the individual and collective process of making sense about science. A guiding principle of RETHINK is that the contextual knowledge of citizens across the EU should play a vital role in shaping future scientific and technological developments and the sharing of this knowledge should be facilitated.

The overall objective of RETHINK is to contribute to making the European science communication ecosystem more open, inclusive, reflexive and adaptive. We aim to improve the quality of interactions between science and society by providing concrete recommendations and training resources for nurturing open and reflexive science-society interfaces.

The RETHINK project brings together 6 partners as well as 4 linked third parties from 10 European countries, integrating scholarly and practical expertise, experimentation and good practices of new approaches in communicating science. It brings together organisations ranging from academia to science centres, from media to technology assessment and a European Sounding Board that league very different backgrounds and areas of expertise.

Tweets por @RETHINKscicomm

RETHINKscicomm retweeted

Journal SciComm @JSciCOM

Great #SummerReading: our special issue on #Communication at the Intersection of #Science and #Politics, coordinated by @birto_faehrich and Alexander Ruserm, available #openaccess at jcom.sissa.it/archive/18/03/truth #power #governance #SciencePolicy #interfases #scicomm #ARRI

27 Jun. 2019

RETHINKscicomm @RETHINKscicomm

Our project coordinator @frankkupper just confessed having stolen an object @experimentarium #Esite2019 cont 🤖 Will this change you perception of him ++ ? We sure

The RETHINK website is a work in progress, and contents will be added as they come available. All public deliverables will be shared on the project website.

Twitter account

Project partners have decided to invest their energies in one social media account, on Twitter, as this channel has proven the most effective for this purpose in past EU-

funded initiatives. Posts with information, content and pictures concerning the project and other related activities are being published regularly on the account since its creation, during the project kick-off meeting.

RETHINK Twitter account: @RETHINKscicomm

Hashtags will include (but are not restricted to):

#scicomm #RRI #mapping #sensemaking #rethinkerspaces #research #SciencePolicy #science #openscience. #SWAFS

All project partners are expected to contribute to the dissemination of project activities through Twitter, by contributing to:

- Follow the RETHINK account, and invite friends and networks to like and follow the account;
- When running RETHINK activities, tweet about it (possibly including pictures) – always tag the @RETHINKscicomm account in all your tweets! – use related hashtags when possible;
- React and interact: like and retweet our tweets, tag relevant contacts if/when it appropriate.

RETHINK-JCOM community page

The creation of a specific RETHINK-JCOM community page will allow for the sharing, testing and collecting of feedback on project outcomes from JCOM visitors, authors and readers, with a fully open access approach. The JCOM community page will serve as a central forum for validation and dissemination of these quality criteria, making use of community tools to collect feedback and contribution from JCOM visitors. Various formats are being explored, with a preference for the Ning platform, for the creation of the community page. The RETHINK-JCOM community page will be launched in the autumn of 2019.

Two JCOM special issues on project research outcomes will also be published throughout the project duration.

Printed promotional material

A project flyer will be produced for the partners to present and promote the project. The flyer will be produced in English and Indesign files will be shared with the partners so that partners can translate it to their local language and print them. SISSA Medialab will take care of the printing of the English version of the project flyer and distribute it to project partners who will request it.

Networks and Related projects

RETHINK will establish direct connections with relevant networks and sister projects (projects funded under the same call) in order to inform them about the project, and to explore future collaborations and partnerships. This list will be extended as the project progresses.

- [Quest](#): QUality and Effectiveness in Science and Technology communication. A two-year sister project of RETHINK, coordinated by Venice International University (VIU).

- [Concise](#): Communication role on perception and beliefs of EU Citizens about Science. Also a sister project of RETHINK, coordinated by Scienceflows.
- [PCST Network](#)
- [Ecsite network](#)
- [ECREA network](#)

Conferences and events

The RETHINK project activities and outcomes will be disseminated at several conference and events. An initial list was provided in M5, within Deliverable 6.6. It will be updated every year.

Exploitation strategy

Our four-step exploitation strategy will be based in dialoguing, reflecting and agreeing what are the products and/or services that we can exploit as legacy of the project. We will begin these conversations in month 12, once we start having some project concrete outcomes, and we will update the exploitation strategy throughout the entire project duration.

1. Project partners will identify the key project exploitation products at the level of each work package and of the project partnership as a whole, in order to support the development of their current activities, and to possibly enable the launch of new ones. This will be done via mapping potential valuable and exploitable results, clarifying types of results and potential users;
2. Within the project Executive Board, we will reflect on how exploitation can be done. We will agree on measures to ensure 'exploitation' of our results by for example:
 - a. Using them in further research activities (outside the action);
 - b. Developing, creating or marketing a product or process.
3. We will discuss how exploitation of our results could be executed either by single partners directly (e.g. for further research) or by others (other beneficiaries or third parties).
4. If needed, we will look for expert advice to access the most appropriate routes for the expected results and how can we deploy them.

Action plan

Clear, effective and wide communication and dissemination of RETHINK activities, events, outputs and outcomes are integral to the project’s success. To engage with a wide variety of stakeholders and attract a growing number of people to participate in our activities, the following action plan has been developed, based on the project main communication objectives:

Objective	Actions	Target audience	Timeframe
Raise awareness about new, effective science communication forms and practices among all the target groups and the broad segment of the public;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share partner’s knowledge, encourage them to use and promote the project social media, community page and website; - Build an audience on social media; - Advocate for the project at events, meetings and conferences; - Reach out to other EU projects; - Support the Rethinkerspaces activities and provide dissemination through Twitter account. 	All	M9-M36
Engage our target audiences with aspirational contents and activities, always in consideration of the need to embrace underserved audiences, considering gender-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide clear guidelines to the project partners, promote the use of Twitter and the RETHINK-JCOM community page for interactions; - Suggested reading: the “Inclusive communication module” by UNICEF; 	Partners and Third Parties	M2 – M36

balanced information and representations;	- Suggested reading: Hypatia good practices .		
Provide a unified approach to communications, including a common public image;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Clear guidelines are provided to the partners; - There is room for adapting the messages in the different languages; - Project logo, visual identity guidelines and template have been shared with partners 	Partners and Third Parties	M1 – M6
Establish sustainable tools and structures for the project including the different communication channels, printed materials, website and social media;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Website and Twitter account have been created and promoted; - The project flyer is being produced and will be shared with project partners; - Regular support project to partners in their dissemination activities and remind them about events, Twitter, etc. will be provided. 	Partners and Third Parties	M1 – M7
Disseminate the outcomes and results of the project to all relevant target groups, enhance the visibility of RETHINK project objectives, activities and outcomes, during all its phases;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disseminate information about RETHINK objectives, activities, outputs and results via the website, social media and RETHINK-JCOM community page; - Issue targeted communication on project landmarks; 	All	M6 – M36

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Build on the partners' contacts, networks and dissemination capacities; - Build interest using social media. 		
Leverage the dissemination potential of all partners and third parties;	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Share clear communication on objectives, governance and deliverables; - Share reminders with detailed plans from partners about delivery dates and contents. - Support project partners in sharing / retweeting / tagging of project news via Twitter. 	All	M6 – M36
Support the communication of the partners at the local and national level.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Follow and support Rethinkerspaces activities, to disseminate the outputs effectively and create a lasting impact. - Keep project website up to date; - Regularly collect updates on partners dissemination activities (past and future). 	Partners and Third Parties	M6 – M36

Monitoring and evaluation

SISSA Medialab will monitor the following indicators to make sure that the project reaches its expected impact:

Website:	10,000 visits by the end of the project.
RETHINK-JCOM community page:	500 users by the end of the project.
Twitter:	1,000 followers by the end of the project.
External workshops, conferences and events	15 presentations
Publications in journals and sector specific magazines	15 publications
Participation in Rethinkerspaces	100+ participants
Final conference	50 participants

All partners will have to report once a year on their dissemination activities. A template, following the European Commission's requirements, will be produced and shared with the partners.

Besides, SISSA Medialab will also send regular updates to partners for them to inform about upcoming events and to fill in a report with details of the events including number of people reached, target groups reached etc.

